

Study on Some Insect Pests of Family Cucurbitaceae from Tha Nat Pin Township, Bago Region

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Abstract

Field survey of cucurbitaceous plants were carried out in Tha Nat Pin Township. The collected specimens were identified and observed infested pest species on cucurbitaceous plants. Monthly population fluctuation of insect pests upon the cucurbits were recorded during the study period. The study period lasted from October, 2015 to February, 2016. A total of twenty species of insect pests on cucurbitaceous plants were observed. These included five species from order Lepidoptera, 11 species from order Coleoptera, three species from order Hemiptera, only one species from order Diptera. Order Coleoptera has most pest species found from this data. Among them 201 individuals of *Aulacophora foveicollis* were highest number of pest and six individuals of *Altica pagana* were lowest number of pest as investigated in this study. Six species were found throughout the study period and recorded as major pests. Host plants and preferential habitat were also observed. Six host plants were white pumpkin, gourd, bitter gourd, pumpkin, cucumber and watermelon. It was found that the most preferred food plant was white pumpkin and gourd. Preferential habitats were leaf, flower, stem and fruit. However, out of the preferred four habitats under and upper side of the leaves were mostly infested.

Keywords: insect, infestation of pests

Introduction

Many insects cause damage by eating or sucking the juice of field crops, vegetables and garden plants or by bringing about disease in them. These are field and garden pests or crop pests. Most of the time, natural enemies and other factors keep the population of pests in sufficiently low levels causing no damage on plants. However, a pest can develop under certain conditions and create situation that requires remedial measures to prevent serious injury to the plant (Ghosh, 1940)

An insect becomes a pest when it does noticeable damage directly or indirectly to man himself or to his livestock, growing crops, stored product or other possessions. Such damage may be of regular or of occasional occurrence and may vary from total loss to a very small fraction (Bainbrigge, 1914). Pests can be classified as follows: (1) regular pest that rarely falls below the economic threshold, (2) sporadic pest that only occasionally rises above the economic threshold, (3) potential pest that might be highly noxious if allowed to become established and pests of special circumstance (Jones, 1974).

Most type of plants are attacked and injured by insects. The injury is caused by insects feeding or ovipositing on the plant or serving as agents in the transmission of plant diseases. This injury may vary from a reduction in crop yields to the complete destruction of the plant (Borror *et al.*, 1976).

Cucurbits under family Cucurbitaceae consists of about 120 genera and 735 species, that are cosmopolitan in mostly tropical and subtropical countries. Many species are cultivated and of economic importance as food plants. Fruits and vegetables of Cucurbitaceous plants are consumed as curries and use in various type of food preparation.

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Cucurbitaceous plants composed mainly of climbing and trailing plants, include bottle gourd, pumpkin, water melon, bitter gourd, cucumber, sweet melon, ribbed luffa, snake gourd, etc. The infestation intensity of insects may vary to some extent in different cucurbits and related to many factors. The activity of insects depends greatly on temperature falls and winters of high latitudes enforce a quiescent period. However, except that in tropics, temperature is less important in determining seasonal activity, but excessive heat of drought and lack of food may enforce a seasonal dormancy (Jones and Jones, 1974).

Bitter gourd contains vitamin A, B₁, B₂ and C as well as minerals like calcium, phosphorous, iron, copper and potassium. The fruit of bitter gourd is similar in nutritional value compared to other cucurbits with the notable exceptions that it is much higher in floride and vitamin C. The vine tips are an excellent source of vitamin A. The medicinal value of the gourd in the treatment of infectious disease and diabetes is attracting the attention of scientists worldwide (Palada and Chang, 2003).

The most important enemies of insects are entomogenous parasitoides and predators. The better known groups of insect predators are members of the orders Odonata and Neuroptera, the Carabidae and the Coccinellidae of the Coleoptera, and Syrphidae of the Diptera (Little, 1974).

Modern pest management relies on planning before planting rather than responding to a pest problem after it has occurred. Gardeners can prevent many insect pest problems by using the knowledge about the pest to make the vegetable planting less suitable for pest development. This could mean planting early to avoid high pest numbers that occur late in the season (Zehnder, 1998).

Mechanical, cultural, biological and chemical controls are main methods of pest control (Talukder, 1993). Cucurbitaceous plants are consumed as edible vegetables and also used as commercial products in all over the world. It is extensively cultivated all over the country. The major pests of these plants include beetles, white fly, leaf hopper, moth, stink bug, melon worm, leaf roller, melon fly and yellow stem borer, which reduce to yield and loss of income to the cultivators. The ecological study of insect pests may be served as a keystone in effective management of these pests on Cucurbitaceous plants. Besides, control of injurious pests with the help of beneficial animals and insects is essential in biological control. Thus the present study was therefore conducted with the following objectives.

- to record and identify the insect pests of cucurbitaceous plants in the study area.
- to study species composition infested on each cucurbitaceous plants in the study area
- to investigate the monthly population fluctuation of recorded insect pests during the study period.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Cucurbitaceous plants cultivated areas is Tha Nat Pin Township. It is situated in eastern part of Bago Region. Study area lies between latitude 17° 30' 19.59" N to 17° 29' 90.73" N and longitude 96° 56' 7.98" E to 96° 87' 43.64" E, situated above the sea level of 13.20 m.

Study period

The present study was conducted from October 2015 to February 2016.

Specimen collection

The insect were collected from different localities such as cucumber field, gourd and white pumpkin field, bitter gourd field, water melon field, and pumpkin field from Tha nat pin township. The insects were picked up by hand. While collecting, specimens were packed in plastic bottle. Damaged or infested parts of the plant were photographed as soon as possible.

Identification and classification

The classification of the specimens were based on Britton, *et al.*, (1970), Hill (1983), Borror, *et al.*, (1998) and Shepard, *et al.*, (1999)

(Source: Google Earth 2016)

Fig.1. Location map of Thanatpin Township

Results

A total of 20 species, 19 genera, 11 families, 10 superfamilies and four orders under Class Insecta were recorded during study period.

Systematic position of studied species (According to Britton, *et al.*, (1970), Hill(1983), Borror, *et al.*, (1998) and Shepard, *et al.*, (1999)).

Phylum	- Arthropoda
Class	- Insecta
Order	- Lepidoptera
Superfamily	- Pyraloidea
Family	- Crambidae
Subfamily	- Spilomelinae
Genus	- <i>Diaphania</i> Hubner, 1818

- Species (1) - *D. indica* Saunders, 1851
 Common name - Leaf roller
 Subfamily - Pyraustinae
 Genus - *Spoladea* Guenee, 1854
 Species (2) - *S.recurvalis* Fabricius, 1775
 Common name - Beet webworm moth
 Subfamily - Schoenobiinae
 Genus - *Scirpophaga* Treitschke, 1832
 Species (3) - *S. incertulas* Walker, 1863
 Common name - Yellow stem borer
 Superfamily - Pterophoroidea
 Family - Pterophoridae
 Subfamily - Pterophorinae
 Genus - *Sphenarches* Meyrick, 1886
 Species (4) - *S. caffer* Zeller, 1852
 Common name - Plume moth
 Superfamily - Hesperioidea
 Family - HesperIIDae
 Subfamily - HesperIinae
 Genus - *Borbo* Evans, 1949
 Species (5) - *B. cinnara* Wallace, 1886
 Common name - Rice swift
 Order - Coleoptera
 Suborder - Polyphaga
 Superfamily - Chrysomeloidea
 Family - Chrysomelidae
 Subfamily - Galerucinae
 Genus - *Aulacophora* Chevrolat, 1836
 Species (6) - *A. foveicollis* Lucas, 1849
 Common name - Red pumpkin beetle
 Species (7) - *A. lewisii* Baly, 1886
 Common name - Pumpkin beetle
 Genus - *Monolepta* Chevrolat, 1837
 Species (8) - *M. signata* Oliver, 1808
 Common name - White spotted beetle

Genus	- <i>Altica</i> Geoffroy, 1762
Species (9)	- <i>A. pagana</i> Blackburn, 1896
Common name	- Metallic blue flea beetle
Subfamily	- Cassidinae
Genus	- <i>Cassida</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Species (10)	- <i>C. circumdata</i> Herbst, 1799
Common name	- Green tortoise beetle
Family	- Cerambycidae
Subfamily	- Cerambycinae
Genus	- <i>Xystrocera</i> Audinet - Serville, 1834
Species (11)	- <i>X. globosa</i> Olivier, 1795
Common name	- Round-headed longhorn beetle
Superfamily	- Cucujoidea
Family	- Coccinellidae
Subfamily	- Coccinellinae
Genus	- <i>Coccinella</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Species (12)	- <i>C. transversalis</i> Fabricius, 1781
Common name	- Transverse ladybird beetle
Genus	- <i>Micraspis</i> Chevrolat, 1837
Species (13)	- <i>M. discolor</i> Fabricius, 1781
Common name	- Non spotted beetle
Genus	- <i>Menochilus</i> Timberlake, 1943
Species (14)	- <i>M. sexmaculatus</i> Fabricius, 1781
Common name	- Lady beetle
Subfamily	- Epilachninae
Genus	- <i>Epilachna</i> Chevrolat, 1839
Species (15)	- <i>E. varivestis</i> Mulsant, 1850
Common name	- Sixteen-spotted ladybird beetle
Superfamily	- Tenebrionoidea
Family	- Meloidae
Subfamily	- Meloinae
Genus	- <i>Mylabris</i> Fabricius, 1775
Species (16)	- <i>M. variabilis</i> Pallas, 1782
Common name	- Blister beetle

Order	- Hemiptera
Suborder	- Sternorrhyncha
Superfamily	- Aleyrodoidea
Family	- Aleyrodidae
Subfamily	- Aleyrodinae
Genus	- <i>Trialeurodes</i> Cockerell, 1902
Species (17)	- <i>T. vaporariorum</i> Westwood, 1856
Common name	- White fly
Suborder	- Auchenorrhyncha
Superfamily	- Cicadelloidea
Family	- Cicadellidae
Subfamily	- Deltocephalinae
Genus	- <i>Nephotettix</i> Macquart, 1835
Species (18)	- <i>N. virescens</i> Distant, 1908
Common name	- Leaf hopper
Suborder	- Heteroptera
Superfamily	- Pentatomoidea
Family	- Dinidoridae
Subfamily	- Dinidorinae
Genus	- <i>Aspongopus</i> Castelnau, 1832
Species (19)	- <i>A. chinensis</i> Dallas, 1851
Common name	- Stink bug
Order	- Diptera
Suborder	- Brachycera
Superfamily	- Tephritoidea
Family	- Tephritidae
Subfamily	- Dacinae
Genus	- <i>Bactrocera</i> Macquart, 1835
Species (20)	- <i>B. cucurbitae</i> Coquillett, 1899
Common name	- Melon fly

Recorded pest species of infested on cucurbitaceous plants during study period

A total of 11 pest species with 584 numbers were infested on white pumpkin during the study period. There were 20 individuals, 3% of *Diaphania indica* were fed on the leaves of white pumpkin, 12 individuals, 2% of *Spoladea recurvalis*, 32 individuals, 7% of *Xylocopa globosa*, 15 individuals, 3% of *Borbo cinnara*, 37 individuals, 6% of *Coccinella transversalis* were also damaged the leaves of white pumpkin. 44 individuals, 8% of *Micraspis discolor*, 30 individuals, 15% of *Monolepta signata*, 61 individuals, 10% of *Menochilus sexmaculatus* were

destroyed large section of plant. The highest infested numbers 201 individuals, 34% of *Aulacophora foveicollis*, and second highest infested numbers 125 individuals, 21% of *A. lewisii* were fed on the leaves of white pumpkin. They were chewing large hole and often leaving on the veins of the white pumpkin leaves. The lowest infested numbers, seven individuals, 1% of *Cassida circumdata* were also damaged (Fig 2, A)(Table 1).

There were observed 12 pest species infested upon gourd during field study. 4% were *Scirpophaga incertulas* and 1% were *Sphenarches caffer*. These two species were observed on the upper side of the leaves and a few on stem. 32% were *A. foveicollis* and 20% were *A. lewisii*, they were serious pest of gourd and found on the leaves, flowers, stem and fruit. 1% were *Altica pagana*, 6% were *C. transversalis*, 10% were *M. sexmaculatus*, 7% were *Epilachna varivestis*, these four beetles were observed on the leaves, 6% were *Mylabris variabilis*, these beetles were found on the upper surface of the leaves and some were found on the flowers and a few on stem, 1% were *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*, 4 % were *Nephotettis virescens* these leaf hopper fed on the leaves of gourd, 8% were melon fruit fly *Bactrocera cucurbitae*, these fly was serious pest of gourd. (Fig 2, B) (Table 1)

Recorded pest species of bitter gourd were *A. foveicollis*, *A. lewisii*, *E. varivestis* and *B. cucurbitae*, infested population as 48%, 30%, 11% and 11% respectively (Fig 2, C) (Table 1).

Pest of pumpkins, such as *A. foveicollis*, *A. lewisii*, *E. varivestis*, *M. variabilis*, these four species were found on leaves, flowers and stems but they prefer the leaves. Infested population on pumpkin as 48%, 30%, 11% and 8%. *Aspongopus chinensis* infestation on pumpkins were found 3% during field survey (Fig 2, D) (Table 1).

A total of four species were found infested on cucumber during field study, namely *A. foveicollis*, *A. lewisii*, *D. indica*, *B. cucurbitae*. Infested population on cucumber as 51%, 32%, 5% and 12% respectively. *D. indica* fed on the leaves, soft stems and fruit of a variety of cucumber but the young were favored succulent leaves (Fig 2, E) (Table 1).

A. foveicollis, *A. lewisii*, *C. transversalis* and *M. sexmaculatus* were also infested upon watermelon. Infested population on watermelon as 47%, 30%, 9% and 14% respectively (Fig 2 F) (Table 1).

White pumpkin and gourd recorded as most infested insect pest of host plants.

Species composition of insect pests on cucurbitaceous plants

A total of 793 individuals of 20 species, confined to 19 genera infested among 15 subfamilies, 11 families, 10 superfamilies and four orders belonging to class Insecta were recorded during the study period. 78 individuals of order Lepidoptera (five species, five genera) these species were *Diaphania indica*, 20 individuals, 26%, *Spoladea recurvalis*, 12 individuals, 15%, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, 24 individuals, 31%, *Sphenarches caffer* seven individuals, 9% and *Borbo cinnara*, 15 individuals, 19% were collected.

Aulacophora foveicollis was recorded the largest number of pest (623 individuals) of Coleoptera and followed by 201 individuals, 32%, *A. lewisii*, 125 individuals, 20%, *Monolepta signata*, 30 individuals, 5%, *Altica pagana*, six individuals, 1%, *Cassida circumdata*, seven individuals, 1%, *Xystrocera globosa*, 32 individuals, 5%, *Coccinella transversalis*, 37 individuals, 6%, *Micraspis discolor*, 44 individuals, 7%, *Menochilus sexmaculatus*, 61 individuals, 10%, *Epilachna varivestis*, 46 individuals, 7% and *Mylabris variabilis*, 34 individuals, 6% were collected.

In order Hemiptera, 45 individuals (three species, three genera), *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*, eight individuals, 18%, *Nephotettis virescens*, 27 individuals, 60%, *Aspongopus*

chinensis, 10 individuals, 22% were collected. The last order Diptera there were 47 individuals (only one species, one genus) was collected (Table 2).

Among the recorded insect pests, order Lepidoptera constituted 25% representing five species, while the remaining order Coleoptera constituted 55% including 11 species, order Hemiptera 15% comprised three species, order Diptera included only one species (Fig 3, A).

A total of 11 families were recorded, among them family Crambidae contributed 15%, Pterophoridae and Hesperidae contributed 5%, Chrysomelidae contributed 25%, Cerambycidae contributed 5%, Coccinellidae contributed 20%, while the remaining family Meloidae, Aleyrodidae, Cicadellidae, Dinidoridae and Tephritidae contributed 5% respectively (Fig 3, B).

Monthly population fluctuation of insect pests on cucurbitaceous plants during the study period

D. indica, *S. recurvalis*, *S. incertulas*, *S. caffer* and *B. cinnara*, of Order Lepidoptera were not found throughout the study period. The first two species were found in two months, remaining three species were found only one month each.

Occurrence of *A. foveicollis* were observed with the numbers of 40 in October, 56 in November, 58 in December, 47 in January and their infestation was recorded throughout the study period. Highest population was recorded in December and lowest population was found in October.

A. lewisii, *C. transversalis*, *M. discolor* and *M. sexmaculatus*, were also recorded throughout the study period. Maximum population of these insects pest were found in December except *C. transversalis* which was in November. Minimum population of *A. lewisii* was found in November and January while the rest in October.

M. signata, *A. pagana*, *C. circumdata*, *X. globosa*, *E. varivestis*, *M. variabilis*, *T. vaporariorum*, *N. virescens* and *A. chinensis* were not found throughout during the study period. The single melon fly *B. cucurbitae* consist in order Diptera was recorded throughout during study period. The highest population was recorded in November, lowest numbers was in October (Table 2).

A. *Diaphania indica*

B. *Spoladea recurvalis*

C. *Scirpophaga incertulas*

D. *Sphenarches caffer*

E. *Borbo cinnara*

F. *Aulacophora foveicollis*

G. *Aulacophora lewisii*

H. *Monolepta signata*

I. *Altica pagana*

Plate 1. Recorded insect pests of Orders Lepidoptera and Coleoptera

K. *Bactrocera cucurbitae*

Plate 2 Recorded insect pests of Orders Coleoptera, Hemiptera and Diptera

A. Collected pest species infested on white pumpkin

B. Collected pest species in fested on gourd

Fig. 2 Percentage of recorded pest species infested on cucurbitaceous plants during the study period

C. Collected pest species infested on bitter gourd

D. Collected pest species infested on pumpkin

E. Collected pest species infested on cucumber

F. Collected pest species infested on watermelon

Fig. 2 Continued

A. Pest species composition with related orders

B. Pest species composition with related families

Fig. 3 Species composition of insect pests with related orders and families from the study area

Table 1 Recorded pest species infested on cucurbitaceous plants during the study period

No	Pest species	Leaf	Flower	Stem	Fruit	Host plants
1	<i>Diaphania indica</i>	✓				white pumpkin, cucumber
2	<i>Spoladea recurvalis</i>	✓				white pumpkin
3	<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	✓		✓		gourd
4	<i>Sphenarches caffer</i>	✓		✓		gourd
5	<i>Borbo cinnara</i>	✓				white pumpkin
6	<i>Aulacophora foveicollis</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	pumpkin, white pumpkin, cucumber, watermelon, gourd, bitter gourd
7	<i>Aulacophora lewisii</i>	✓	✓			pumpkin, white pumpkin, watermelon, gourd, bitter gourd, cucumber
8	<i>Monolepta signata</i>	✓				white pumpkin
9	<i>Altica pagana</i>	✓				gourd
10	<i>Cassida circumdata</i>	✓				white pumpkin
11	<i>Xystrocera globosa</i>	✓				white pumpkin
12	<i>Coccinella transversalis</i>	✓				white pumpkin, watermelon, gourd
13	<i>Micraspis discolor</i>	✓				white pumpkin
14	<i>Menochilus sexmaculatus</i>	✓				white pumpkin, watermelon, gourd
15	<i>Epilachna varivestis</i>	✓				pumpkin, gourd, bitter gourd
16	<i>Mylabris variabilis</i>	✓	✓	✓		pumpkin, gourd
17	<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>	✓				gourd
18	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	✓				gourd
19	<i>Aspongopus chinensis</i>	✓				pumpkin
20	<i>Bactrocera cucurbitae</i>	✓			✓	gourd, bitter gourd, cucumber

Table 2 Monthly population fluctuation of insect pests on Cucurbitaceous plants during the study period

No	Pest species	Populations				Total
		October	November	December	January	
1	<i>Diaphania indica</i>	-	-	12	8	20
2	<i>Spoladea recurvalis</i>	-	-	8	4	12
3	<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	24	-	-	-	24
4	<i>Sphenarches caffer</i>	-	7	-	-	7
5	<i>Borbo cinnara</i>	-	-	15	-	15
6	<i>Aulacophora foveicollis</i>	40	56	58	47	201
7	<i>Aulacophora lewisii</i>	32	30	33	30	125
8	<i>Monolepta signata</i>	-	12	18	-	30
9	<i>Altica pagana</i>	-	-	-	6	6
10	<i>Cassida circumdata</i>	-	-	7	-	7
11	<i>Xystrocera globosa</i>	-	-	14	18	32
12	<i>Coccinella transversalis</i>	7	13	9	8	37
13	<i>Micraspis discolor</i>	4	12	16	12	44
14	<i>Menochilus sexmaculatus</i>	6	15	22	18	61
15	<i>Epilachna varivestis</i>	36	10	-	-	46
16	<i>Mylabris variabilis</i>	25	9	-	-	34
17	<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>	-	-	-	8	8
18	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	20	7	-	-	27
19	<i>Aspongopus chinensis</i>	10	-	-	-	10
20	<i>Bactrocera cucurbitae</i>	5	17	13	12	47
Total		209	188	225	171	793

Discussion

The present study on some insect pests of Family Cucurbitaceae from Tha Nat Pin Township, Bago Region embodied 20 pest species confined to 19 genera and infested pest among 15 subfamilies, 11 families, 10 superfamilies and four orders. It was recorded all beetle species, represented the suborder Polyphaga. Under the order Hemiptera, three suborders were studied and described. In the present work, order Diptera was recorded single Suborder.

The order Lepidoptera, consist of three families, Crambidae, Pterophoridae and Hesperidae has been studied and described. Under the order Coleoptera, four families, Chrysomelidae, Cerambycidae, Coccinellidae, Meloidae were recorded. The collected three families of order Hemiptera were Aleyrodidae, Cicadellidae and Dinidoridae. Under the order Diptera, only one family Tephritidae was collected.

Observed pest species included *Aulacophora foveicollis* (red pumpkin beetle), *A. lewisii* (blue pumpkin beetle), *Monolepta signata* (white spotted beetle), *Altica pagana* (metallic blue flea beetle), *Cassida circumdata* (green tortoise beetle), *Xystrocera globosa* (round-headed longhorn beetle), *Coccinella transversalis* (transverse ladybird beetle), *Micraspis discolor* (non spotted beetle), *Menochilus sexmaculatus* (lady beetle), *Epilachna varivestis* (sixteen-spotted ladybird beetle), *Mylabris varibilis* (blister beetle), *Diaphania indica* (leaf roller), *Spoladea recurvalis* (Beet webworm moth), *Scirpophaga incertulas* (yellow stem borer), *Sphenarches caffer* (plume moth), *Borbo cinnara* (rice swift), *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (melon fly), *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (white fly), *Nephotettix virescens* (leaf hopper), and *Aspongopus chinensis* (stink bug).

Among four species of beetle pests were recorded. *A. foveicollis*, *A. lewisii* and *E. dodecastigma* were found to be major pests. Red pumpkin beetle, *A. foveicollis* was ranked as widespread and important pest in tropical countries including Myanmar (Nair, 1995; Morris and Waterhouse, 2001).

Aulacophora foveicollis, *A. lewisii*, *Epilachna dodecastigma*, *Bactrocera cucurbitae* and *B. dorsalis* were found to be major pests. This finding coincides with the finding of Hill (1983) that *A. spp*, *E. varivestis* and *B. sp* were found to be major pests of cucurbitaceous plants in my present study.

Stink bugs were observed throughout the study period and sucked the juice of stem causing wilt of the plant and rather distinguishing on account of the buggy smell. Although they occasionally prove very serious (Crowe, 1985), they are sometimes reported as minor pest in cucurbitaceous plants (Nair, 1995, Hla Hla Htay, 2009, Yee Yee Cho, 2009). In the present study, the attack of stink bugs on cucurbitaceous plants were not serious and they were found to be minor pests.

The infestation of *A. foveicollis* was notable in the present study and nearly 45% of the leaves were left with skeleton due to large biting holes of the beetles. The damage of beetles may kill the seedlings. Red pumpkin beetle, *A. foveicollis* was also recorded as the major pest in other cucurbitaceous plants (Phyu Phyu Soe, 2008, Hla Hla Htay, 2009, San San Htay, 2009 and Yee Yee Cho, 2009). Infestation of *A. foveicollis* was observed throughout the year and population density was higher in monsoon crop than winter crop. It seems to be fact that temperature and relative humidity may influence the development of this beetle. This finding was in agreement with the findings of previous authors (Roy and Pande, 1991, Nair, 1995, Morris and Waterhouse, 2001, Phyu Phyu Soe, 2008, Hla Hla Htay, 2009, San San Htay, 2009 and Yee Yee Cho, 2009).

Aulacophora lewisii was found together with *A. foveicollis*, however there are less abundant. It was active throughout the study period and peak population was observed in

monsoon crops. Infested plant became wilt and death in seedling. Attacked flowers were unmarketable due to the biting holes on the anthers. This finding agrees with the finding of previous authors (Nair, 1995, Morris and Waterhouse, 2001, Yee Yee Cho, 2009 and San San Htay, 2009). However, it contrast with the finding of Hla Hla Htay (2009) that *A. lewisii* was the minor pest on bitter gourd.

The major pest *Epilachna dodecastigma* was found throughout the study period. They were more abundant in monsoon crop than winter crop. It contrasts with the finding of previous authors (Ghosh, 1940, San San Htay, 2009, Yee Yee Cho, 2009). *Epilachna varivestis* were not found throughout the study period.

Pest species selected their specific microhabitats on the host plant. Same type of microhabitat was utilized by allied species since they have the same behaviour to response the environmental factors and mode of life. It is in accordance with the statement of Wyniger (1962).

Wood (1989) and Waterhouse (1993) stated that red pumpkin beetle, twelve-spotted lady beetle, pumpkin leaf roller, fruit fly and melon aphids are economic important pests due to yield loss of cucumber. However, in the present study, these pests except melon aphid were considered serious pests which mainly damaged host plant.

In the present study, sexual dimorphism is observed in *Diaphania indica* Saund. The adult female had orange-coloured anal tuft of hair and which distinguished it from the male. As the larvae grow, two white longitudinal lines gradually appear and stage of the larva was mainly based on the head width. This finding is in accordance with the reported by Nair (1995).

In conclusion, the frequency of insect appearance depends on the presence of favourable habitats, moreover, the fluctuation of pest population number and occurrence of insect pests in cucurbitaceous plants may be concerned with the pest control measures. The knowledge obtained from the present study about the microhabitat utilization of the pests and the identification of the insect pests may be useful for effective and successful pest management in horticulture.

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